

Exploration of Identity and Cultural Hybridity in Mukherjee's Jasmine and Lahiri's Namesake; A Comparative Study

Dr. Upasana Bharati

Professor
Faculty of Science and Humanities
Major S.D. Singh University
Farrukhabad, Uttar Pradesh, India

Sumit Kumar Misra

Research Scholar
Faculty of Science and Humanities
Major S.D. Singh University
Farrukhabad, Uttar Pradesh, India

Abstract

This comparative study analyzes Bharti Mukherjee's Jasmine and Jhumpa Lahiri's The Namesake focusing on the themes of identity and cultural hybridity. It provides a deep understanding of the immigrants' experiences and struggle as in cultural negotiation and identity formation in an alien land. In Jasmine, the journey of an Indian woman has been presented who reinvents herself and adopts different identities as she goes across different cultures, symbolizing the fabricate and fluid nature of identity. Lahiri's The Namesake presents the generational conflict as the immigrants struggle for preserving their cultural heritage and to fit in the society of the host country. Using the framework of comparative study, this study examines that the both novels present the social and psychological challenges of intermingling faced by the protagonists, focusing on the negotiation between the traditional values and modernity.

Key words: Hybridity, immigrants, experience, negotiation, identity, fabricate fluid, generational, conflict, preserving, cultural heritage, intermingling etc.

Introduction

Diasporic Literature is a reflection of the experiences of the people who migrated from their home land to other countries with various purposes like personal goals, higher education, to seek better opportunities, improvement in quality of life, economic stability, or materialistic pursuits. This movement might also be forced like fleeing from oppression or war. Diaspora studies focus on the many cultures and experiences of individuals who live in alien shore, emphasizing the writers' sense of loss and nostalgia. It reflects various approaches like blending of cultures and the emotional struggle of the people who moved from their home land to other countries. The sense of nostalgia, rootlessness, exploration of identity, multiculturalism and experience of immigrants are the main themes of Diasporic Literature.

This study is an attempt to examine the themes of identity and cultural hybridity in Bharti Mukherjee's 'Jasmine' and Jhumpa Lahiri's 'The Namesake' and also to make comparison on the theoretical approach in their narratives. The novels focus on the lives, experience and

struggle of immigrants to reconcile dual cultural identities and also the complexities and difficulties faced by them in new land. In the novel *Jasmine*, Bharti Mukherjee has presented the journey of an Indian woman who adopts different names as her different identities as she moves from one place to another. Her ability and strength of adaptation the changing environment and reshaping herself to fit the surroundings have been highlighted. The novel expostulates that the identity can be flexible and ever changing of the people specially living in alien land. Lahiri's *The Namesake* portrays the challenges and the struggles of first generation immigrants, Ashoke and Ashima, who tries to preserve their Indian tradition while adopting the new culture of America. Gogol, the second generation immigrants, faces challenges with his dual identity and adapting two cultures as Indian and American.

1.1: Identity

The quest for identity is the common theme of diasporic literature. Identity is the sense of self and it comprises the aspects like personality traits, appearance, social roles, experiences, cultural associations, nationality, religion, language and personal values. It is the way in which people become aware to themselves and how they are considered and recognized by others in the society. Exploration of identity is the journey of self-realisation, the immigrants try to understand and discover who they are and struggle between two cultures. It becomes difficult for immigrants to recognize in other countries and they also face challenges to mingle in new culture and to change their life style. In the novels of Bharati Mukherjee's *Jasmine* and Jhumpa Lahiri's *The Namesake*, the main characters struggle to find out their identity. In *Jasmine*, the protagonist changes her identity many times as she becomes Jasmine from Jyoti and Jane from Jasmine, she leaves her past and tries to fit in the new environment. In *The Namesake*, Gogol Ganguli also trying to find out his belongings as he struggles to make balance between Indian heritage and modernity of America. The challenges between modern life and cultural heritage have been highlighted in both novels, and how this affects the search of individuality. It becomes difficult for immigrants to recognize in other countries and they also face challenges to mingle in new culture and to change their life style

1.2: Culture Hybridity

In diasporic literature cultural hybridity refers the merging or mixing of different cultures, identities, values and traditions when people migrates from their home land to another country and come into contact. It shows that as people migrate from their own culture to new culture how their identity changes. They adapt the elements of new culture and preserve the elements of their own culture that shows the experiences of the both navigating between the two cultural worlds. Diasporic writers such as Bharti Mukherjee, Jhumpa Lahiri, Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni etc. use the theme of cultural hybridity in their works to present the issues of migration, belongingness, and exploration of selfhood.

The concept of Third Space and Cultural Hybridity given by Homi K. Bhabha provides a structure for analysing the discussion of identity and multiculturalism in diasporic literature. Bhabha explained The Third Space as an 'in between' where cultures are mixed and the meaning

of culture is reshaped that becomes a challenge for the thought of pure and separate culture. The new blended identity is raised. In the same way cultural hybridity represents the combining of various cultures arising a new form of identity which challenge the idea that culture is fixed. Applying these concepts to Mukharjee's *Jasmine* and Lahiri's *The Namesake* shows that identity is flexible and changeable. In *Jasmine* the journey of the protagonist through different cultures adapt the new environments adjusting herself in different situations. She interacts with different cultures and people and make changes in herself various times which shows that her identity is changed by her experiences. Similarly in *The Namesake*, Gogol struggles between two cultures, Indian cultural heritage and his upbringing in American Culture. He tries to find out his place between two cultures. Both novels highlight that diasporic identity is not fixed but changeable. It is a dynamic process and shaped by adaptation, adjusting and personal growth rather than unchanging of oneself and understanding of selfhood.

Purpose of the study

1. To explore how the protagonists struggle with identity issues as they mix in new culture and society. It aims to analyse the main character's sense of change in response to displacement from their home land.
2. To study the concept of cultural hybridity and how it is used and represented by these diasporic writers in their novels. It also focuses on blending of different cultures, clashing and adjustment and the experience of the immigrants living in align shore.
3. To examine the themes of migration, displacement and sense of selfhood and also their relationship between tradition and culture of their homeland and new environment.
4. To contribute in the study of diasporic literature by providing a comparative analysis between Bharti Mukherjee's *Jasmine* and Jhumpa Lahiri's *Namesake* focusing on diasporic themes with their perspectives.

3. Exploration of Identity and Cultural Hybridity

3.1 Exploration of identity and cultural hybridity in *Jasmine*

Bharti Mukherjee is well known as Indian-born American diasporic writer. She moved to America in 1960s and became naturalized citizen of the country. She has deeply explored the experiences, difficulties and challenges of Indian immigrants to the United States of America. She has used the theme of identity crises, immigration, blending of different cultures and experience of the people living in other country. She has made a prominent contribution to the field of diasporic literature.

The exploration for identity and cultural hybridity are the central themes in Mukherjee's *Jasmine*, as the main character covers a transformative journey of selfhood. The story begins with a small village named Hasnapur in India where she is known as Jyoti as her name symbolizes the Indian culture and her domestic identity. The early life of the protagonist has been presented

with social expectations and traditional values. Her identity in the beginning reflects her bond with her cultural roots which personifies innocence and domination. Jyoti States as “A daughter had to be married off before she could enter heaven, and dowries beggared families for generation. Gods with infinite memories visited girl children on women who needed to be punished for sins committed in other incarnation. (Jasmine, P. 39)”

Her Exploration of identity is represented with her arrange marriage with Prakash. He renames her from Jyoti to Jasmine which shows her movement from traditional life to the modernity and beginning of the transformation of her identity. He encourages her to think and dream beyond her upbringing in the traditional family and to be ambitious and self-determined. Prakash says to her, “You are small and sweet and heady, my Jasmine. You’ll Quicken the whole world with your perfume” (Jasmine, p. 77). It symbolizes the beginning of Jasmine’s identity.

The tragic turn comes in the life of Jasmine when Prakash is killed in a bomb blast. Jasmine becomes a young widow and she decides to fulfil the dreams of Prakash of going to America. She says that “Prakash has taken Jyoti and created Jasmine, and Jasmine would complete the mission of Prakash. She begins her journey to the United States leaving behind her past life in India in search of the new identity. She becomes mentally prepared to adapt identity transformation. She faces various challenges on arriving in America as she is immigrant without legal document and totally unaware about the new world. She is exploited and raped by a Half-Face man; she kills her attacker in self-defence which shows another transformation to rebuild her life.

The identity of the protagonist remains changing continuously as she moves from one place to another and adopts new names and roles. She adopts a new name ‘Jane Ripplemeyer’ as she becomes caretaker and domestic partner of a banker named Bud Ripplemeyer. She delves herself as Jane in rural life adopting the identity of home maker to survive in the American society. She states that “My grandmother may have named me Jyoti, Light, but in surviving I was already Jane, a fighter and adopter (Jasmine, p. 40).

She adopts another identity as Jase when she comes into relationship with Taylor and his family in Newyork and delves into urban life. Jasmine gets a sense of belongingness and acquiescence seeing Taylor’s endearment, kindness and praising for her. She is happy to be a part of the family, she likes to be called as day mummy by Duff, Wylie calls her as caregiver and Taylor calls her as Jase. She adopts her changing identities as she says “But Jyoti was now a sati-goddess; she burned herself in a trash-can-funeral pyre behind a boarded-up motel in Florida. Jasmine lived for future, for Vijn & Wife. Jase went to movies and loved for today (Jasmine, p. 176).”

After the death of her husband, Jasmine’s journey as an immigrant is full of pain, survival, and transformation which force her to adapt diverse identity. Her journey is not related only one identity or one culture but continuously keep on changing and moving forward. Mukherjee

has presented Jasmine as a mixed character combining her Indian Culture and experience of alien shore.

Mukherjee has presented the theme of cultural hybridity. The protagonist does not belong to India or America completely but creates a new mixed identity that mingles the culture of the both country. The story of the novel explores how immigrants immerse in different cultures. Her transformation from Jyoti to Jasmine, Jase, and in the last Jane Ripplemeyer presents the cultural negotiation. While adopting western culture cumulatively, she retains the memories of her own cultural values and beliefs.

3.2 Exploration of identity and cultural hybridity in The Namesake

The novel explores generational gap between Gogol and his parents, Ashoke and Ashima. His parents desire to follow the Bengali customs and traditions but he feels disconnected from the expectations of their parents. On the other hand, Ashima finds it difficult to follow American culture and way of living and she holds on to Bengali customs and traditions. “For being a foreigner, Ashima is beginning to realize, is a sort of lifelong pregnancy—a perpetual wait, a constant burden, a continuous feeling out of sorts” (The Namesake, p. 49). It focuses on the experience of first generation immigrants about their struggles of mixing and cultural displacement. On the contrary, Gogol desires to follow American culture in relation to carrier choices and social relationship that results the conflict with his parents. His relationship with Maxine is distancing him from his family and his cultural heritage.

In The Namesake, Lahiri represents the theme of identity especially in the context of cultural hybridity, belongings, self-discovery and experience of first and second generation immigrants. She has presented the complexities of personal identity and societal expectations through the life of Gogol Ganguli. The name of the protagonist symbolizes his struggle to reunite his Indian roots with his upbringing in America. The novel highlights the psychological turbulence that results from the cultural hybridity. Ashok and Ashima, his parents, name him on the name of a Russian writer Nikolai Gogol which has a deep significance as in a train accident Ashok’s life was saved while reading a book of this Russian Writer. His name symbolizes his father’s past and his own struggle for his selfhood. He fails to see the essential value of his name and instead his name becomes for him the source of burden, disconnection and embarrassment as the writer says “He hates having to explain. He hates having to tell people that it does not mean anything in Indian. He has been told that it is Russian. He hates that the first thing his parents gave him is something that he wants to cast off.”(The Namesake,p. 76)”. He decides to change his name legally to Nikhil represents his attempt to control over his own identity. His disappointment with his name highlights his internal conflict between his Bengali heritage and his wish to adapt an American Identity. “He hates that his name is both absurd and obscure, that it has nothing to do with who he is, that it is neither Indian nor American but of all things Russian.” (The Namesake,p.76). Later he ascertains that changing his name cannot erase his heritage. His mother gifted him a book at the end of the novel which denotes his reuniting with his cultural roots.

Gogol's journey represents the struggle of second generation immigrants who torn between cultural acclimatization and nostalgia of his hereditary roots. In the beginning of the novel, he rejects his identity as a Bengali and desirous to adapt the identity as an American. He, generally, does not want to participate in the Bengali customs and tradition and also avoid participating in the cultural gathering with his parents. He is in the romantic relationship with an American lady named Maxine symbolizes his wish to delve himself in the modern western culture that is against of his parents' ethics. He enjoys of their culture spending time with the family of Maxine. He feels that his Bengali culture makes him different from his American friends. He begins to see his parental roots in a new way after the death of his father when he follows Bengali traditions shaving his head and it reveals his liaison to his family and cultural heritage.

4: Comparative Analysis:

Both the novels 'Jasmine' by Bharti Mukherjee and 'The Namesake' by Jhumpa Lahiri examine the theme of identity and cultural hybridity within the diasporic experience. The works explore the difficulties and struggle of the immigrants as they delve between the tradition of their homeland and modernity of the host country. They have presented different approach of adapting new identity. This analysis will focus on the similarities and differences in their perspectives.

4.1: Similarities in the exploration of identity and Cultural Hybridity:

Migration of the main characters from the home land to align shore plays an important role in shaping the identity. In 'Jasmine' the protagonist adopts new identities at multiple times as she moves forward and travels from India to the United States. Similarly, in the 'Namesake' the struggles of Gogol Ganguli with his name and cultural heritage have been represented that reveals confliction of second generation immigrants' in the host country. Both protagonists deal with the experience of displacement, which coerce them to redefine and adopt their new identities in the new country. Except it both the novels explores the conflicts between the cultural heritage and modernity. Jasmine struggles to make balance between her Indian abidance and American Culture. Her journey reflects chasing her personal freedom making distance from unpalatable traditions. Similarly, Gogol's journey represents counteraction with his parents' expectations as he attempts to adapt modern life style and tries to fit himself in the society of America. In both the novels, the protagonists struggle between the realities of new environment and roots of their cultural heritage. Cultural Hybridity is the main theme in the selected novels as the main characters accept the phases of their own native and adopted culture. Jasmine desirous to survive in America therefore she continuously adopts new names as her identity and reinvent herself which symbolizes the theme of identity in diasporic literature. On the other hand, dissatisfaction and struggle of Gogol with his name symbolizes the acceptance of hybrid identity gradually.

4.2: Differences in the exploration of identity and Cultural Hybridity:

The major difference between Jasmine and The Namesake is the projection of genders in the narratives. In Jasmine, the journey of female protagonist has been presented who changes

her identity and reinvent herself according to the new environment neglecting the social values. On the other hand, male protagonist has been presented in 'The Namesake' whose struggle for identity is internal and changes on the basis of family expectations. The story of Jasmine is based on the survival of the protagonist while the story of The Namesake is about the self-discovery and acceptance.

In Jasmine, The narrator explores the transformation of individual protagonist focusing on resiliency and personal reinvention. She adopts new identity escaping herself from her past. While in The Namesake, family relationship and expectations have been focused. Gogol's struggles for his identity are influenced by family expectations and the experience of first generation immigrants. Both novels deal with the same idea about dream in America but the interpretation is different. Jasmine looks America as the endless possibilities where she can transform herself and can also make herself free from the social norms which incorporate the idea that identity is not fixed. On the other hand, Gogol faces challenges with growing up between the two cultures, Indian and American,. He feels uncertainty and alienation and this conflict between two cultures ties with his American dream. It shows the differences in the approach of the both novelists in the identity formation. The novels Jasmine and The Namesake examine the theme of cultural hybridity and the quest for identity within the experience of immigrants and also deal with as migration is the process of the transformation. But the narratives are different; Mukherjee focuses on reinvention of an individual while Lahiri explores struggle of a family and two generations of immigrants. The perspectives of both of the novelists are same and provide the deep sense of understanding about the complications related to the quest for identity and cultural hybridity.

5: Conclusion:

The study of Jasmine by Bharti Mukherjee and The Namesake by Jhumpa Lahiri denotes how the writers have used the theme of identity and cultural hybridity into their narratives of displacement, migration, selfhood, cultural assimilation. Both the novels deal with the struggle of protagonists with their identities as they delve between their cultural heritage and the culture of host country. Jasmine presents the struggle for individual's reinvention and adaptation to survive in an alien land while The Namesake portrays the struggle and conflict of the second generation immigrant scrambling with his familial cultural roots. The study emphasizes that the identity is not constant but it is reshaped through personal experiences, self-reflection, and cultural interactions.

6: References:

1. Mukherjee, Bharathi. Jasmine. New York: Gross press, 1989. Print.
2. Mukherjee, Bharati. The Tiger's Daughter. New Delhi: Penguin Books (India) Ltd.2014.
3. Lahiri, Jhumpa. The Namesake. Boston, United States: Houghton Mifflin, 2003 Print.
4. Lahiri, Jhumpa. The Lowland. New York, United States: Alfred A, Knopf/Random House, 2013 Print.

5. Bhatia, Sunil. "American Karma: Race, Culture and Identity in the Indian Diaspora." New York University Press, 2007.
6. Bhabha, Homi K.. "The Location of Culture". Routledge New York, 1994.
7. Paulraj, J. Albert Vincent. "Cultural Studies in Bharathi Mukherjee's Jasmine." JETIR, vol. 6, Mar. 2019.
8. Sankar, G. and Dr. R. Soundarayan. "Immigrant Experience and Self Identity in Bharati Mukherjee's Jasmine: A Study." Scholedge International Journal of Multidisciplinary & Allied Studies, Vol. 04, 2017.
9. Yadav, Kiran and Dr. L. K. Tiwari. "Struggle for Identity in Bharti Mukherjee's 'Jasmine'". International Journal of Food and Nutritional Sciences. Vol. 8, 2019.
10. Kumari, Ranjeeta. "The Theme of Diaspora in the Novel of Jhumpa Lahiri". Vol. 9, Jan. 2021.
11. Macwan, Hiral Joseph. "Identity Crisis in Jhumpa Lahiri's 'The Namesake'". International Journal of English Language, Literature and Humanities. Vol. II, 2015.
12. Mohammadi, Amirmohammad. "Jhumpa Lahiri's The Namesake Through the Lens of Diaspora Literature." International Journal of Management and Humanities (IJMH), vol. 11, Sept. 2024.
13. Tiwari Ray, Shobha. "Diasporic Consciousness in Jhumpa Lahiri's Novel The Namesake." Universal Research Reports, vol. 11, Feb. 2024.
14. Macwan, H.. Struggle for identity and diaspora in Jhumpa Lahiri's The Namesake. International Journal of Humanities and Social Science Invention, 2014.